

STEM vs non-STEM differences in university teaching and research during the COVID-19 pandemic: the case of Sri Lanka

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Citation:

de Silva, T. & Wickramasinghe, V. (2022). STEM vs non-STEM differences in university teaching and research during the COVID-19 pandemic: the case of Sri Lanka. International Journal of Educational Management, 36(5), 678-693. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-07-2021-0272>

This Version is available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-07-2021-0272>

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Abstract

Purpose This research aims to explore differences between STEM and non-STEM disciplines in terms of the changes to teaching and research practices caused by the Covid-19 pandemic.

Design/methodology/approach The paper analyses survey responses collected between July and November 2020 from 241 academics (excluding library staff) from the five oldest state universities in Sri Lanka. The analysis focuses on differences between STEM and non-STEM faculty using multiple linear regression to control for demographic characteristics such as age, gender and designation as well as university specific factors.

Findings The paper finds significant differences in the teaching practices of STEM and non-STEM academics, both in terms of preparation time for teaching as well as tools used for online delivery. Significant differences are also observed in research practices, with STEM faculty being significantly more likely to engage in research collaborations, obtain research funding, and be involved in more research projects. We do not find any evidence of the pandemic having differential impacts on research productivity between the broad disciplines.

Originality/value This research provides insights into differences between STEM and non-STEM disciplines in online teaching and research practices adopted since the onset of the pandemic, which are important for formulating appropriate policy responses to mitigate the impact of the pandemic on both students and staff. The contribution is particularly significant for developing countries where the creation of a skilled workforce is a key driver of the development process.

Keywords Covid-19, online teaching, research practices, STEM vs. non-STEM differences, university academics

Paper type Research paper

1 Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic has had a tremendous impact on how the higher education sector operates, both students and staff having had to transition to working online in a short period of time. This has been particularly challenging in developing countries where resource constraints exist in terms of internet connectivity and device availability, and support for the preparation and delivery of online teaching material has been limited (World bank, 2020). The repercussions of this change are likely to vary across academic disciplines which differ in terms of the type of pedagogical content and commonly used instructional methods, type of students, and type of research conducted.

The first nationwide Covid-19 lockdown in Sri Lanka took place in March 2020 and continued until mid-May 2020. All schools and universities were closed for students during this time, though some institutions switched to online instruction almost immediately after the physical closures. By June 2020, it is estimated that close to 90 percent of students were able to access online higher education, with higher participation rates in the sciences (e.g. 95 percent in dental and medical sciences) than in the non-science fields (e.g. 74 percent in the arts and humanities) (Hayashi et al., 2020). Universities opened for face-to-face teaching briefly in September 2020 but the onset of the second wave of infections in the country led to the universities

reverting to and remaining with online instruction since then. The prolonged disruptions to face-to-face teaching have forced universities to innovate, not only in terms of delivery of teaching and assessment, but also in terms of how research and administrative work is conducted to ensure the continuous functioning of these institutions. This was facilitated by the intervention of the government to provide internet access to learning management systems and video conferencing facilities used by state universities free of charge to both students and staff, though issues of device availability and network coverage remain (Hayashi et al., 2020).

In this context, this paper uses data collected from a survey of university academics (excluding library staff) from the state higher education sector in Sri Lanka to explore differences between the sciences (encompassing science, technology, engineering, and mathematics, or STEM disciplines) and other disciplines (including social sciences, arts, and humanities) in terms of the changes to teaching and research caused by the Covid-19 pandemic. Specifically, the study aims to investigate differences in online teaching and research practices between academics in STEM and non-STEM disciplines and identify whether the onset of the Covid-19 pandemic affected the broad disciplines differently.

By focusing on these aspects, this study makes significant contributions to the literature on higher education with important implications for the turbulent period that the higher education sector is currently experiencing. First, this research examines potential differences in how STEM and non-STEM faculty have responded to the pandemic situation in terms of their teaching and research. While there is a body of evidence documenting differences in teaching methods and research practices between STEM and non-STEM disciplines (see, for example, Kara *et al.*, 2021; Lindblom-Ylänne *et al.*, 2006; Laird *et al.*, 2008; Eagan, 2016; Uddin *et al.*, 2021) as well as on the impact of Covid-19 in the STEM fields (Brancaccio-Taras *et al.*, 2021; Owston *et al.*, 2020; Seaman *et al.*, 2021), there is less evidence on the differences between disciplines in their responses to the pandemic. Understanding these differences is important for formulating institutional and policy responses to ensure that the learning outcomes of all students, as well as the working conditions and productivity of staff is not compromised. Second, while most of the literature is based on developed countries, this paper provides a developing country perspective where resource constraints and academic culture are likely to be different. Given that higher education, and science education in particular, is seen as a key driver of economic growth in many developing countries, this paper highlights the need for timely institutional interventions to mitigate adverse effects on students and staff and prevent disruptions to the creation of the skilled workforce needed for the development process.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews the related literature and Section 3 describes the data collection and analysis methods used in this paper. Section 4 presents the results. The next section provides a discussion of the findings and presents some managerial implications. The final section concludes.

2 Related literature

STEM education at both secondary and tertiary levels has been studied by many, where common themes among studies that make comparisons between STEM and other disciplines include gaps in gender and minority representation, and differences in teaching practices. The gender gap in science, in particular, has been well-documented with disparities observed in terms of career progression, research output, and general job satisfaction (Casad *et al.*, 2021; Griffith and Dasgupta, 2018; Holman *et al.*, 2018; Sà *et al.* 2020). The gender gap in the sciences has received renewed attention with the onset of the pandemic, with evidence

suggesting that the increased burden of caregiving, which is disproportionately borne by women, following the closure of school and childcare facilities, will give rise to widening gaps in research productivity (Anderson *et al.*, 2020; Vincent-Lamarre *et al.*, 2020; Wehner *et al.*, 2020). Based on this body of evidence, we control for gender when examining differences between STEM and non-STEM faculty.

There are several studies that compare teaching practices and methodologies between STEM and non-STEM fields. There appears to be a consensus that, at least in the developed countries where much of this research is based, academics in STEM fields favour teacher-centered approaches to teaching. For instance, based on a study of academics from Finland and the United Kingdom, Lindblom-Ylaine *et al.* (2006) find that the hard disciplines tend to be less student-centric and that these differences between disciplines are stronger than within-discipline differences between applied and pure subgroups. In more recent work, Eagan (2016) finds that while there has been an overall trend in higher education towards student-centered teaching and active learning, this shift has been slower in the STEM fields, where traditional lectures and curve-based grading still feature prominently.

Laird *et al.* (2008) take this finding a step further to examine student learning outcomes arising from these different teaching approaches. They show that students in STEM are less likely to achieve deeper levels of learning and that faculty expectations for integrative and reflective learning also tend to be lower in these fields. The potential barriers to adoption of the types of active learning strategies that facilitate deeper levels of learning include logistical constraints like limited time to cover the breadth of required content, rewards for research rather than teaching, and perceptions about students being reluctant to participate (Bathgate *et al.*, 2019).

There is also a growing body of research on the use of blended learning and online teaching in STEM fields after the onset of the Covid-19 pandemic, though few make comparisons between STEM and non-STEM fields. One such project by Owston *et al.* (2020) compares the performance following and perceptions about blended learning between students in STEM and non-STEM courses. The research finds that STEM students performed significantly better though their perceptions about the course were more negative. These results are consistent with survey evidence presented by Seaman *et al.* (2021) on the barriers to online STEM education - lack of student engagement and motivation being among the key challenges cited by academics. The authors also discuss the perception among STEM academics that teaching their subjects pose unique challenges in an online environment given the requirement for conducting practicals and laboratory sessions. These findings tie in with work by Pagoto *et al.* (2021), Brancaccio-Taras *et al.* (2021) and Means and Neisler (2020) who posit that a possible problem with shifting to online teaching in the STEM fields has been that many teachers merely switched to delivering lectures online and providing recordings of labs, thereby meeting only the immediate needs of the students. The authors suggest that in the long-term, online delivery needs to be carefully designed to ensure the students do not lose out on important learning outcomes and provide some examples of innovative methods used by STEM academics in this aspect.

There is less work on research productivity differences between disciplines, though there are several studies that focus on interdisciplinary research and how some fields (e.g. biomedical research or the health sciences) are more interdisciplinary than others (such as international relations or astrophysics) (Van Noorden, 2015). Several studies also find that STEM projects generally have a better chance of getting funding, resulting in rewards for projects with a greater STEM aspect (Bromham *et al.*, 2016; Pedersen, 2016; Uddin *et al.*, 2021). In line with this, there is some anecdotal evidence that the organizational culture

for STEM disciplines in research-oriented universities is leans more towards support and rewards for grant production and competition than non-STEM disciplines (Byrne and Cave, 2020).

Table I provides a summary of the key studies that focus on differences between STEM and non-STEM higher education. There is relatively little research focusing on these differences in light of the recent changes caused by the ongoing pandemic. As such, we build on the dimensions identified in Table I, with an emphasis on changes to teaching and research practices that arose after the onset of the Covid-19 pandemic. Moreover, our paper presents a developing country perspective on university academics and their work practices in terms of both teaching and research – relatively unexplored areas in the literature.

[Table I here]

3 Methods

Figure 1 summarizes the research methodology followed in this study and is described in detail in the following subsections.

Figure 1 Research methodology

3.1 Survey of university academics

This study assesses the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on university academics using data collected through a survey targeting academic staff in five state universities in Sri Lanka. These five universities were selected given that they are the oldest universities in the state university system and commenced online teaching and learning, in at least some of their academic faculties, soon after the closure of the universities’ premises to students.

The survey was administered via an online questionnaire which was emailed to all members of the permanent or probationary academic staff excluding academic staff members attached to libraries.¹ Contact details for academics were obtained from university websites and the questionnaire was emailed between

¹ In the Sri Lankan university system, academic staff refers to both the staff in conventional academic departments as well as libraries. In this paper, we focus on permanent academic staff excluding library staff so in what follows, we refer to non-library academic staff members when using the term “academics”.

the months of July and November 2020. Responding to the questionnaire was voluntary, respondents could decline to answer any of the questions, and identifiable information was not collected from the respondents.

The University Grants Commission (UGC) (2020) states that in 2019, there were 3,196 permanent or probationary members of the academic staff excluding library staff in the five universities targeted by our survey. We were able to successfully send out the questionnaire to 2,846 academics and received responses from 241 members of our target population. Table II compares the distribution of academics across disciplines, educational qualifications, and designations in our sample to those observed in the population using the UGC (2020) statistics.

[Table II here]

3.2 Measures

To achieve the objectives of the study, the survey was designed to capture the dimensions identified in Table I. Accordingly, the administered questionnaire composed of four key sections – background characteristics including educational qualifications and years of experience in academia; information on teaching and research practices following the Covid-19 disruptions; information on time use; and attitudes to online teaching and learning. The details of the measures used are as follows.²

Background characteristics of respondents. Information on educational qualifications and years of experience in academia. In addition, information was collected on post-graduate degree programs in which academics are currently enrolled. An academic is categorized as being in a STEM field based on his/her reported faculty.

Research practices and productivity. Information on the number of ongoing research projects and postgraduate research students being supervised, the presence of collaborators, having obtained research funding as a principal investigator, and the importance of different resources for conducting research. We also collected information on how Covid-19 has affected research productivity, including access to resources required for research and work-related international travel.

Online teaching practices. Information was gathered on teaching practices adopted after the COVID-19 pandemic, including modes of instruction, the time required for preparation for online teaching, and constraints faced during online teaching. The questions on constraints faced in online teaching were administered using Likert scales.

Information on time use before and during the Covid-19 period. The section on time use required respondents to indicate how many hours during an average five-day workweek they spent on work-related activities such as teaching, research, administrative work and commuting, and non-paid activities such as domestic unpaid work, caring for dependents, and sleep, before and during the pandemic period. Given the presence of outlier responses, the responses were converted to shares of hours spent on paid work (teaching, research, administrative work, and commuting) to ensure comparability between respondents.³

We exclude academics currently enrolled in full-time postgraduate education from the analysis of time use and teaching practices.

3.3 Empirical analysis

We examine differences in teaching and research practices between STEM and non-STEM university academics, with a focus on how the onset of the pandemic may have impacted these practices. Given that

² The question items pertaining to these measures are provided in the Appendix.

³ Following conventions in time-use literature we refer to domestic work and caregiving collectively as unpaid work.

an academic's belonging to a STEM or non-STEM discipline as well as their work-related practices are likely to vary systematically based on demographic characteristics as well as institutional features specific to a university, we use multiple linear regression analysis so that we can control for these factors. Accordingly, for each measure of interest y_i , we estimate the following:

$$y_{ic} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 STEM_{ic} + \theta X_{ic} + \alpha_c + u_{ic} \quad (1)$$

Where y_{ic} is the specific research or teaching measure of interest for academic i working in university c , $STEM_{ic}$ is an indicator for whether the academic is from a STEM discipline, X_{ic} is a vector of individual characteristics such as age, gender, and academic designation, and α_c refers to university-specific fixed effects. u_{ic} is a stochastic disturbance term. The model is estimated using OLS, with robust standard errors. For comparison, we report the estimate of β_1 which captures the mean difference between STEM and non-STEM academics after controlling for demographic and institutional characteristics and the raw mean difference between the two groups for each dependent variable of interest.

4 Results

4.1 Demographic and job characteristics

We start by examining differences in terms of demographic characteristics and designation among the academics in STEM and non-STEM disciplines. Table III reports these differences. We see that while there is a significantly lower share of female academics in STEM, academics in STEM disciplines also tend to be significantly older, are more likely to have a Ph.D. or equivalent educational qualification, and accordingly, are more likely to be in the post of senior lecturer or higher. Subsequently, academics in non-STEM disciplines are significantly more likely to be enrolled in postgraduate education. These observed demographic differences between STEM and non-STEM academics justify our choice of the empirical model for examining differences in teaching and research practices.

[Table III here]

Given the potential for confounding effects of gender, age, and university-specific factors in influencing the probability of having a Ph.D. or equivalent qualification, we estimate a linear probability model as specified in Equation (1) with the regressand a dummy variable for whether a respondent has a Ph.D. or equivalent. We find that while controlling for these effects, particularly age, does moderate the STEM vs. non-STEM difference, the overall conclusion does not change – academics in STEM disciplines are still significantly more likely to have a Ph.D. or equivalent qualification than those in non-STEM disciplines.

4.2 Online teaching practices

Next, we examine whether there are any differences in the online teaching practices adopted by university academics, by broad discipline. Table IV presents the mean difference between STEM and non-STEM academics before and after controlling for demographic and institutional characteristics for different outcomes related to online teaching practices. Note that the mean difference after controlling for these factors is the β_1 coefficient from estimating Equation (1).⁴

[Table IV here]

⁴ The sample becomes slightly smaller when confounders are controlled for so the sample size for the values in column (4) is smaller. Using this smaller sample for computing raw differences yields results that are very similar to those reported here.

The results in Table IV show that there are significant differences between STEM and non-STEM faculty in terms of the time taken to prepare for a single course unit in a given week, both with and without controlling for age, gender, designation, and university. We also see that the STEM faculty teach a larger number of course units, though this difference becomes insignificant when the controls are added. In terms of the share of teaching hours in total paid working hours, there are no differences between STEM and non-STEM academics.

The lower panel of Table IV highlights differences in the resources used for online teaching. The estimates suggest that STEM faculty are more likely to use voice-recorded PowerPoint presentations and interactive content and less likely to recommend reading material or use social media than their non-STEM peers. These differences in the types of material used for teaching may explain the increased preparation time reported by STEM academics. They also highlight possible systematic differences in instruction between disciplines that cannot be explained away by the age of the academic or university in which he/she works.

The next set of results look at differences in constraints faced in online teaching; in particular, we explore the share of academics who report being affected (moderately or severely) by the different institutional, student, and personal factors. The results in Table V show that there are no differences between broad disciplines in terms of the institutional, student, or personal factors related to online delivery. The only difference is in STEM faculty being more likely to respond that the subjects that they teach require more hands-on attention than can be given with online instruction. This is likely driven by the large role of laboratory sessions or clinicals in STEM education.

[Table V here]

4.3 Research productivity

The second part of our analysis explores potential differences in research practices between disciplines and possible differential impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on research productivity. Table VI highlights several differences between the STEM and non-STEM fields in terms of research. In particular, STEM faculty report being involved in a larger number of research projects and are more likely to report engaging in regular research collaborations and having obtained research grant funding than their non-STEM counterparts, even after controlling for age and university characteristics. These results provide evidence in favour of differences in research practices between STEM and non-STEM academics in Sri Lanka.

[Table VI here]

Building on these differences in research practices, we next explore differences in the types of resources highlighted as being very important for the research productivity of university academics. As expected, some differences between disciplines emerge, particularly in terms of the importance of laboratories and physical research equipment and in the use of research assistants. The former emphasises differences in the type of research carried out whereas the latter is possibly linked to the number of projects – if STEM faculty are engaged in multiple research projects at a given time, research assistance would be important for maintaining progress on these projects. There are no differences in terms of the importance of having human subjects or conducting fieldwork for research.

Table VII investigates the impact of Covid-19 on research by assessing differences between disciplines in the extent to which access to research resources was affected. The results indicate that there are no differences between STEM and non-STEM academics in this regard. Subsequently, we find that there have

not been any differential impacts on research productivity as measured by the number of new projects started since the onset of the pandemic, time spent on research, or disruptions to work-related travel.

[Table VII here]

5 Discussion of findings

In this study, we examined differences in teaching and research practices between STEM and non-STEM academics, with an emphasis on the changes brought about by the Covid-19 pandemic. Our analysis suggests significant differences between disciplines, not only in terms of the profiles of the academics in the different disciplines but also in terms of the research and teaching practices of the two groups.

The gender disparity of a higher prevalence of women in non-STEM fields than in STEM that we observe in our results is consistent with international evidence on gender gaps in the sciences (Griffith and Dasgupta, 2018; Holman *et al.*, 2018). This is attributed to many reasons starting from female students having fewer female role models, women having lower social capital in the form of networks and recognition, gaining their promotions slower, and being more likely to leave their jobs (Casad *et al.*, 2021; Holman *et al.*, 2018; Sà *et al.* 2020). The disparity between disciplines in terms of the educational qualifications of university academics has also been noted in the Sri Lankan context (it is unlikely to arise in countries where university academics are only hired upon completion of a Ph.D.). As discussed in Dundar *et al.* (2017), while faculties in the STEM fields have larger shares of faculty holding doctorates, this has important implications for teaching, particularly of postgraduates, and the research outputs of the institution.

Given these differences in the aggregate profiles of STEM and non-STEM university academics in Sri Lanka, we proceed to explore differences in teaching and research practices between disciplines. In terms of research, we do not observe any differential impacts of the pandemic on the research productivity of STEM and non-STEM faculty. This is not particularly surprising – much of the available evidence on the impact of the pandemic indicates that it is the gender gap within disciplines that is widening (Anderson *et al.*, 2020; Vincent-Lamarre *et al.*, 2020; Wehner *et al.*, 2020). However, we do find evidence of differences in research practices and productivity between groups that potentially pre-date the pandemic. We see that STEM academics are involved in a larger number of research projects, are more likely to have obtained research funding during their academic career and have a research group or engage in regular research collaboration. These findings are consistent with the statistics produced by the National Research Council of Sri Lanka (2021), which indicate that a large share of the high-impact research produced by Sri Lankans is in the sciences. It is likely that the lower probability of forming research networks and lower availability of competitive grant funding in the non-science fields contribute to this disparity. The international literature suggests that while there are differences in the extent of interdisciplinary research between disciplines, projects that have a greater STEM orientation have better chances of obtaining funding (van Noorden, 2015; Bromham *et al.*, 2016; Pedersen, 2016; Uddin *et al.*, 2021). There is also some evidence that the organizational culture in STEM disciplines is more oriented towards research and grant funding (Byrne and Cave, 2020).

In terms of online teaching, we find that lecturers in the STEM fields tend to report longer preparation times for their online teaching, which can be explained (at least in part) by the types of teaching materials they use for online instruction. For instance, STEM faculty tend to report using more voice-embedded PowerPoint presentations and interactive materials than their non-STEM colleagues. Given that these involve asynchronous learning material, by design, they involve longer preparation times. While nearly all

lecturers in our sample use the Zoom video conferencing facility to conduct synchronous teaching sessions, it is interesting that non-STEM faculty are more likely to use social media such as WhatsApp and Facebook groups in their teaching.

These differences, particularly the higher prevalence of voice-embedded presentations, are consistent with the evidence that STEM teaching in higher education tends to be more teacher-centric than other disciplines (Bathgate *et al.*, 2019; Eagan, 2016; Felder, 2021; Lindblom-Ylance *et al.*, 2006). While work by Laird *et al.* (2008) goes further to show that there are lower expectations of and opportunities for integrative and reflective learning for STEM students due to these differences in teaching approaches, recent work in the context of the pandemic shows that STEM students find pre-recorded lectures less effective than having hybrid instruction and multiple modes of learning and student engagement (Pagoto *et al.*, 2021) and that student satisfaction among students taking STEM courses is lower both before and after the move to online teaching and learning (Means and Neisler, 2020). While we do not collect information on student perspectives and learning outcomes arising from teaching differences between STEM and non-STEM faculty in Sri Lanka, a comparative analysis of online teaching methods and student outcomes across disciplines in Sri Lanka would be an interesting area of future research.

We also find that STEM faculty are more concerned that the nature of the subjects they teach is less conducive to online instruction. This is possibly due to the heavy reliance on lab work and practicals in teaching in these fields. These concerns appear to be universal among STEM academics around the world – as highlighted in Brancaccio-Taras *et al.* (2021), many STEM academics are concerned that students no longer get the hands-on experiences that make them feel like scientists. However, there is increasing evidence of successful initiatives undertaken by scientists to address this challenge, such as increasing the use of research articles and case studies to engage learners, and designing online labs and research experiences for students (Brancaccio-Taras *et al.*, 2021; Owston *et al.*, 2020). Indeed, Seaman *et al.* (2020) argue that while STEM teachers have a perception that teaching their subjects online poses a unique challenge, there are potential learnings that can be taken from the non-STEM disciplines that also involve practicals, such as music and dance. Accordingly, provision of professional development facilities for STEM staff that introduce these best practices in online instruction can be useful for improving student engagement and ensuring that STEM students continue to meet their intended learning outcomes.

More generally, many of the academics surveyed (across all disciplines) indicated facing constraints to teaching online, with more than 40 percent of academics flagging connectivity and device issues among students. Given the rapid transition to online instruction, problems related to lack of technological infrastructure albeit at varying intensities are common in many developing countries (see, for example, Zarei and Mohammadi, 2021; Joshi *et al.*, 2020; Gautam and Gautam, 2021; Aminuddin, 2021). For instance, universities vary in terms of availability of online learning management systems, students' access to devices and internet connectivity (which is in large part dictated by socioeconomic background) and technical know-how of academic staff, while countries may also differ in terms of reliability of power supply and internet coverage. Within this context, Sri Lanka appears to have made the shift to online teaching and learning relatively well – according to Hayashi *et al.* (2020), an estimated 90% of university students had participated in online education by June 2020, a level of access comparable to developed countries like Japan, supported by free access to university web servers from all internet service providers until August 2020. However, the problem of maintaining student engagement remains even when resource constraints faced by staff and students are less severe (Baticulon *et al.*, 2021; Rafi *et al.*, 2020; Seaman *et al.*, 2021). While the initial response of many academics has been to simply convert face-to-face teaching

to synchronous online lectures (Brancaccio-Taras *et al.*, 2021; Rapanta *et al.*, 2020), as we progress into the second year of living and working with the pandemic, it will be essential to revisit the design of online learning activities and assessments to enhance digital teaching and learning.

5.1 Managerial implications

Our findings have important managerial implications for both the short-term, where the Covid-19 pandemic continues to affect the higher education system, as well as the long-term. Short-term recommendations include:

- Provision of professional development facilities for academic staff to provide exposure to best practices in online instruction and assessment to ensure active learning and achievement of learning outcomes (particularly in STEM subjects that involve practicals and laboratory work)
- Setting up mechanisms to ensure that students with lack of access to devices or internet connectivity are not unfairly disadvantaged (e.g. student loan facilities to purchase devices, provision of on-site facilities to limited numbers of students who are unable to engage in online learning from their homes, and free or subsidized internet access for education purposes)
- Investing in infrastructure that can facilitate high quality online instruction and integrity of assessments (e.g. secure browser software or harnessing new technologies such as blockchain)

Longer-term recommendations to address systemic differences between STEM and non-STEM fields include:

- Facilitation of doctoral education for faculty members and encouraging direct recruitment of PhD qualified academics, particularly in non-STEM fields
- Taking measures to enhance research output among non-STEM academics by promoting interdisciplinary research collaborations, introducing competitive grants schemes for non-STEM research projects, etc.

5.2 Limitations

This study has some limitations. First, even though the distribution of academics by educational qualification and designation is reasonably well replicated in our sample (see Table I), females are slightly overrepresented, as are academics with doctorates and professors. Second, the study focuses on the five oldest state universities in the countries, where the educational profile of academic staff as well as the constraints faced by academics and students are likely to be different from the other state universities in Sri Lanka. However, results from a survey on online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic which covered all state higher education institutions on the constraints to teaching and learning (Hayashi *et al.*, 2020) are similar to those presented here, suggesting that while the extent of the problem may vary in magnitude across universities, qualitatively they are not very different.

6 Conclusion

In this paper we explored differences between STEM and non-STEM disciplines in terms of the changes to teaching and research practices caused by the Covid-19 pandemic, using survey responses from academics from the five oldest state universities in Sri Lanka. We find evidence of significant differences in teaching practices, both in terms of preparation time and tools used for online delivery, as well as in research practices, with STEM faculty being significantly more likely to engage in research collaborations, obtain research funding, and be involved in more research projects. However, we do not find any evidence of the pandemic having differential impacts on research productivity between the broad disciplines. These results

highlight the need for short-term interventions to ensure high quality online or blended learning to achieve learning outcomes as well as long-term measures to address disparities between the broad disciplines in terms of human resources and research outputs.

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Tables

Table I. Summary of key previous studies on STEM non-STEM differences

Dimension of STEM non-STEM differences	Key insights	Sources
Gender gap	Female academics in STEM fields face greater barriers in terms of career progression, research output, job satisfaction	Casad <i>et al.</i> , 2021; Griffith and Dasgupta, 2018; Holman <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Sà <i>et al.</i> , 2020
	Gender gaps in research productivity widening as a result of increased burden of caregiving for women following COVID-19 pandemic	Anderson <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Vincent-Lamarre <i>et al.</i> , 2020; Wehner <i>et al.</i> , 2020
Teaching practices	STEM fields more likely to favour teacher-centered approaches to teaching with a slower shift to active learning methods	Lindblom-Ylanne <i>et al.</i> , 2006; Eagan, 2016; Laird <i>et al.</i> , 2008
	STEM students less likely to achieve deeper levels of learning due to constraints faced by faculty such as heavy teaching loads, rewards to research, etc.	Laird <i>et al.</i> , 2008; Bathgate <i>et al.</i> , 2019
Blended and online learning	Lower student satisfaction about following STEM courses online, potentially due to type of instruction used (e.g. more teacher centric techniques such as lecture recordings)	Pagoto <i>et al.</i> , 2021; Braccaccio-Taras <i>et al.</i> , 2021; Means and Neisler, 2020
	Heightened perception of constraints to teaching STEM courses online due to importance of practical work and labs	Seaman <i>et al.</i> , 2021
Research productivity	Wider availability of funding for STEM projects resulting in rewards for research projects with greater STEM component	Bromham <i>et al.</i> , 2016; Pedersen, 2016; Uddin <i>et al.</i> , 2021
	Organizational culture more geared towards securing grant funding for research in STEM disciplines	Byrne and Cave, 2020

Table II. Distribution of academic staff in the sample and target population by sex, educational qualification and designation

	Distribution of all academics		Distribution of STEM academics	
	Sample	Population	Sample	Population
<i>Discipline</i>				
STEM	0.68	0.62		
Non-STEM	0.32	0.38		
<i>Sex</i>				
Male	0.39	0.51	0.43	0.50
Female	0.61	0.49	0.57	0.50
<i>Educational qualification</i>				
Bachelor's degree	0.13	0.19	0.11	0.20
Master's or equivalent	0.18	0.22	0.08	0.13
Mphil or equivalent	0.07	0.11	0.07	0.09
PhD or equivalent	0.62	0.49	0.74	0.58
<i>Designation</i>				
Lecturer	0.29	0.27	0.23	0.33
Senior Lecturer	0.59	0.53	0.52	0.51
Professor	0.21	0.20	0.25	0.16

Note: Statistics on the population of university academics are computed using data from UGC (2020).

Table III. Job characteristics and educational qualifications

	non-STEM	STEM	Sig
Share female	0.69	0.57	0.078*
Mean age	40.30	44.64	0.002***
Mean years of experience	11.41	13.51	0.139
<i>Education</i>			
Share with PhD or equivalent	0.40	0.74	0.000***
Share currently enrolled in PG education	0.39	0.23	0.012**
<i>Designation</i>			
Share of senior lecturer or higher	0.61	0.77	0.012**
Share of professors	0.16	0.24	0.123

Note: The last column reports the p-value for two-sided independent sample t-tests or chi-squared tests of proportions. Significance levels: * 0.1 ** 0.05 *** 0.01

Table IV. Online teaching practices

	Without controlling for confounders			Mean difference after controlling for confounders
	STEM	non-STEM	Mean difference	
<i>Online teaching practices</i>				
Mean number of units taught online	1.95	1.76	0.19*	0.13
Mean time taken to prepare per course per week	10.18	7.63	2.55*	3.03**
Mean student contact time per course per week	4.83	6.31	-1.48	-0.46
Teaching hours (as a % of paid hours) before Covid	0.39	0.37	0.02	0.02
Teaching hours (as a % of paid hours) after Covid	0.47	0.43	0.04	0.05
<i>Tools used for online teaching (share using)</i>				
Voice embedded PPT	0.63	0.45	0.18*	0.22**
Video recordings	0.59	0.60	-0.01	-0.02
Web resources	0.38	0.43	-0.05	-0.06
Reading material	0.86	0.95	-0.09*	-0.08
Interactive material	0.45	0.33	0.12 ^a	0.15*
Social media	0.43	0.64	-0.21***	-0.16*

Note: The table shows the mean value for STEM and non-STEM academics for each variable (columns 1 and 2) along with the raw mean difference (column 3) and the mean difference after controlling for confounders as captured by the β_1 coefficient estimated in Equation 1 (column 4).

Significance levels: * 0.1 ** 0.05 *** 0.01 ^a One-sided test significant at 10% level.

Table V. Issues faced in online teaching

<i>Share reporting online teaching affected by the following:</i>	Without controlling for confounders			Mean difference after controlling for confounders
	STEM	non-STEM	Mean difference	
Share with experience in distance learning	0.34	0.33	0.01	0.04
Lack of expertise in online delivery	0.20	0.26	-0.06	-0.04
Subject requires more hands-on attention	0.70	0.46	0.24***	0.27***
Students' lack of devices	0.45	0.60	-0.15*	-0.08
Students' lack of engagement	0.45	0.54	-0.09	-0.03
Lack or limited functionality of LMS	0.08	0.16	-0.08 ^a	-0.03
Poor internet connectivity	0.45	0.52	-0.07	-0.03
Lack of suitable recording devices/software	0.31	0.35	-0.04	0.03

Note: The table shows the mean value for STEM and non-STEM academics for each variable (columns 1 and 2) along with the raw mean difference (column 3) and the mean difference after controlling for confounders as captured by the β_1 coefficient estimated in Equation 1 (column 4).

Significance levels: * 0.1 ** 0.05 *** 0.01 ^aOne-sided test significant at 10% level.

Table VI. Research practices

	Without controlling for confounders			Mean difference after controlling for confounders
	STEM	Non-STEM	Mean difference	
<i>Research productivity</i>				
Mean number of research projects currently involved in Supervising PG research students (senior lecturer and above only)	3.77	2.73	1.04***	0.86**
Do not have frequent research group or collaborators	0.85	0.8	0.05	0.02
Have obtained research funding as principal investigator (senior lecturer and above only)	0.05	0.26	-0.21***	-0.17***
Undertake work-related international travel (senior lecturer and above only)	0.82	0.63	0.19**	0.23***
	0.77	0.71	0.06	0.03
<i>Share reporting the following resources as very important for their research productivity</i>				
Laboratory/physical research equipment other than computer	0.470	0.17	0.30***	0.33***
Computing or library resources that are not available remotely	0.310	0.36	-0.05	-0.05
Research assistants/research student collaborators	0.530	0.26	0.27***	0.18**
In-person human subjects for experiments/research	0.350	0.40	-0.05	-0.1
Research field sites	0.290	0.36	-0.07	-0.11
Conferences, research symposia	0.370	0.47	-0.10 ^a	-0.09

Note: The table shows the mean value for STEM and non-STEM academics for each variable (columns 1 and 2) along with the raw mean difference (column 3) and the mean difference after controlling for confounders as captured by the β_1 coefficient estimated in Equation 1 (column 4).

Significance levels: * 0.1 ** 0.05 *** 0.01 ^aOne-sided test significant at 10% level.

Table VII. Impact of COVID-19 on research productivity

	Without controlling for confounders			Mean difference after controlling for confounders
	STEM	Non-STEM	Mean difference	
<i>Share reporting that COVID-19 affected the following:</i>				
Ability to engage in discussions with collaborators	0.300	0.450	-0.15**	-0.13
Ability to find/hire research students/assistants	0.510	0.430	0.08	0.00
Ability to carry out research work (accessing literature, data collection, analysis)	0.520	0.540	-0.02	-0.03
Ability to present/disseminate research at conferences, workshops, seminars	0.590	0.550	0.04	0.01
Ability to obtain funding	0.510	0.510	0.00	0.02
<i>Research productivity</i>				
Started new projects during COVID-19 pandemic	0.53	0.6	-0.07	-0.12
Research hours (as a % of paid hours) before COVID	0.26	0.25	0.00	-0.04
Research hours (as a % of paid hours) post COVID	0.28	0.30	-0.02	-0.05
Travel plans disrupted by COVID	0.47	0.45	0.02	0.01

Note: The table shows the mean value for STEM and non-STEM academics for each variable (columns 1 and 2) along with the raw mean difference (column 3) and the mean difference after controlling for confounders as captured by the β_1 coefficient estimated in Equation 1 (column 4).

Significance levels: * 0.1 ** 0.05 *** 0.01